

Original Article

Orthodontic Bracket Slot Deformation While Segmental Torqueing in a Bracket-Archwire Segment Assembly: An FEA Study

Varadaraju Magesh¹, Pandurangan Harikrishnan^{2*}, Shubham Dubey¹, Aman Kumar¹, Balamani Arayambath³

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, College of Engineering and Technology, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Kattankulathur, Chengalpattu 603203, Tamil Nadu, India

²Teeth"iN" Jaws Center, Lake Area, Nungambakkam, Chennai 600034, Tamil Nadu, India

³Department of Orthodontics, MGPG Institute of Dental Sciences, Pondicherry 605006, India

Received: 7 September 2025

Accepted: 18 September 2025

Published online: 30 September 2025

Keywords: orthodontic brackets, archwire, slot deformation, finite element analysis, segmental torque

Orthodontics is a field of dentistry treating malocclusions using fixed appliances consisting of a brackets, archwires, ligatures etc. Few studies showed the tie wings and slot deformation of single orthodontic bracket-archwire assembly. The objective of this study was to analyse the slot deformation in two orthodontic brackets-archwire segments during torque. Conventional 0.018 inch Stainless Steel (SS) and Titanium (Ti) brackets were modelled using a reverse engineering approach. Modelled brackets-archwire segment assemblies were meshed using Finite Element Analysis (FEA) software. SS archwire was torqued (twisted) from 0° to 30° with 5° increments. The brackets slot deformation in the top, middle and bottom locations of the slots were measured using FEA software. The 0.0173" x 0.0253" SS archwire with 0.0183" width Ti bracket showed the maximum deformation of 54.03 µm in the top location of slot, whereas the 0.0163" x 0.0223" SS archwire with 0.0183" SS bracket showed the minimum deformation of 21.87 µm in the top location of slot. This *in-silico* study visualizes the slot deformation in a two brackets-archwire system similar to clinical situation during segmental torque.

© (2025) Society for Biomaterials & Artificial Organs #20018725

Introduction

Malocclusion is the improper alignment of teeth that affects the function and aesthetics of face. Patients irrespective of the age seeking malocclusion treatment is growing every day. Orthodontic specialists treat malocclusion using components of fixed appliances namely orthodontic brackets, archwires, ligatures etc. These components work with the principle of mechanics. Archwire generated torque applied on the tooth through brackets facilitate refining the tooth movement during the last stages of treatment. Due to the applied labial crown or lingual root torque, brackets are subjected to stress, strain and deformation. Experimental and FE Studies extensively evaluated bracket systems relevant to torque. [1-3]. Few studies quantified stress generated in the brackets and

archwires [4,5]. Experimental studies showed using digital image correlation technique that the tie wings in the brackets are deforming due to the application of archwire torque [6,7]. An experimental study showed that the bracket tie wings are strained by the force application [8].

Finite element (FE) and experimental studies showed that the single bracket slot deformation as a contributory factor for torque loss [9-11]. A FE study showed that the slot deformation is higher compared to tie wings deformation as the slot has direct contact with twisted archwire using single brackets [12]. Another FE study showed that the tie wings are rotated during the archwire torque [13]. FEA is an excellent tool that helps to test the mechanical behavior of structures without extensive experimentation and instruments and is widely used in the field of dental biomechanics. Sometimes excessive deformation in the bracket leads to tie wings fracture which needs replacement of the bracket and thus increase in the cost of the treatment. All these studies showed that stress, strain and deformation is applied on brackets irrespective of the

* Corresponding author

E-mail address: teethnjaws01@gmail.com (Dr. Pandurangan Harikrishnan, Craniofacial Orthodontist, Teeth"iN" Jaws Center, Lake Area, Nungambakkam, Chennai 600034, Tamil Nadu, India)

Table 1: Bracket top slot deformation in 0.018" bracket with archwires used in this study

Angle of twist (degree)	Slot location deformation with SS archwire (µm)			
	0.016" x 0.022"		0.017" x 0.025"	
	SS bracket	Ti bracket	SS bracket	Ti bracket
0°	0	0	0	0
5°	0.18	0	3.39	3.88
10°	3.41	4.23	10.43	12.90
15°	7.74	10.54	17.75	22.77
20°	12.38	17.14	25.26	32.84
25°	17.17	24.43	32.88	43.12
30°	21.87	31.84	40.52	54.03

materials, size and types of brackets. If the bracket slot deforms due to the archwire applied torque, then the torque expected by the clinician may not be transferred to the tooth. Clinically, archwire torque is applied in segments of two or four teeth in the anterior region during the treatment. This study on segmental brackets slot deformation is required to understand the deformation behavior. To the best of our knowledge there are no experimental or FE studies available for the slot deformation in the bracket-archwire segment. So, the aim of this study was to analyse the slot deformation in the two brackets-archwire segments during torquing using FEA.

Materials and Methods

Conventional SS 0.0183" slot width maxillary central incisor bracket was modeled using reverse engineering approach. The bracket (Leone SpA, Quaracchi, Italy) dimensions were measured using Vision

measuring system with an inbuilt software as shown in figure 1a. The bracket dimensions were measured in all the orientation as shown in figure 1b. Solid modeling software (SolidWorks Corp. Dassault Systemes, Vélizy-Villacoublay, France) was used to model the bracket. In this study, SS and Ti left and right central incisor brackets were simulated. So, one bracket model was duplicated into two brackets for a segmental analysis. The inter-bracket distance was kept as 4 mm. for clinical simulation. The Solidworks software was used to model the 0.0163" x 0.0223" and 0.017" x 0.0253" SS archwires. The archwires were assembled in the two bracket segments as shown in figure 1c. The two bracket-archwire segment assembly was imported in the analysis software (Ansys Workbench 2024R1, Ansys Inc, USA) for FE meshing and analysis.

Due to the smaller size bracket radius geometry, the mesh convergence was not performed in this analysis. For the accurate results the assembly was meshed with a fine mesh using four noded iso-parametric tetrahedral elements. The mesh quality was checked using Jacobian, aspect ratio values within the range. In the contact faces of brackets with archwire, bonded, no-separation and frictionless connections were established. The SS and Ti materials were assigned with Young's modulus of 200000 MPa and 114000 MPa respectively. The Poisson's ratio of SS and Ti materials were 0.30 and 0.31 respectively [14-16]. All degrees of freedom of all the nodes in the bracket base were fixed. A structural, linear and isotropic analysis was performed. Archwire was twisted from 0° to 30° angle of twist simulating palatal root torque with in increments of 5° using remote displacement at the end faces of the archwire as shown in figure 1d. From the proximal side of the brackets, the nodal deformation in the top, middle and bottom locations of the slot were measured in both occlusal and gingival side walls. This measurement was done when the archwire contacts the bracket slot walls.

Figure 1: Modeling and analysis of two brackets-archwire segment: a) Vision Measuring System (VMS) used to measure bracket dimensions, b) Measurement of bracket dimensions, c) Solid modelling of two brackets-archwire assembly, d) Boundary condition of a bracket and archwire, e) Finite element analysis showing deformation of the two brackets segment, f) line diagram of deformation pattern in the anterior view of tie wings

Results and Discussion

The deformation in the bracket slot deformation is vital as it has direct contact with the archwire during torque. In our study, the decreasing order of slot deformation was seen in the top, middle and bottom slot locations. This was due to the cantilever nature of top slot location of the slot. Due to the rigid base the deformation in the bottom slot was less. Literature also showed similar deformation behavior in slot walls [9,11]. The top slot location deformation in 0.0183" SS and Ti brackets with 0.0163" x 0.0223" and 0.017" x 0.0253" SS archwires is presented in table 1.

For 30° angle of twist in 0.0163" x 0.0223" SS archwire, the bracket top slot location deformation in the 0.0183" SS and Ti bracket were 21.87 µm and 31.84 µm respectively. Similarly, for 30° angle of twist in 0.0173" x 0.0253" SS archwire, the bracket top slot location deformation in SS and Ti brackets were 40.52 µm and 54.03 µm respectively. Closer to our results an experimental study using single bracket archwire showed that for 30° angle of twist in 0.0163" x 0.0223" and 0.0173" x 0.0253" SS archwire, the bracket top slot location deformation in the 0.0183" SS bracket were 28.40 µm and 41.90 µm respectively [11]. In our study, the top slot location deformation was less compared to their study due to the two bracket segments.

Distal tie wings of both brackets showed more deformation, and the deformation was reduced gradually towards the mesial tie wings. There was nil deformation in the mesial tie wings of both brackets as shown in figure 1e. But, in single bracket deformation study both mesial and distal side slots were deformed equally [10,11]. In this study, the archwires were twisted after it was placed inside the bracket slot. But clinically the twisted archwire is placed inside the bracket slot. This phenomenon of reduced bracket slot deformation was due to the reduction of torque transfer from the distal ends towards the mesial ends of archwire as shown in figure 1f, the line diagram of deformation pattern in anterior view of the tie wings. As the palatal root torque was applied, the deformation in the gingival wings and slots were higher compared to occlusal side as shown in figure 1e. Similarly, a FE study showed higher deformation in the gingival wings compared to the occlusal side wings due to the applied palatal root torque [10]. The SS bracket is stiffer than the Ti bracket which produced more deformation. There are no studies available for slot deformation in the segmental brackets in the literature. This study showed the deformation behavior of the segmental brackets to torque forces which is relevant to commonly done clinical torqueing in the anterior segments.

The limitation of this study is that the tooth, various bracket size and different bracket types and archwire materials were not analysed. Further, experimental studies are required to evaluate the cause for deformation in the distal tie wings slots and nil deformation in the mesial tie wings slots.

Conclusion

This *in-silico* study visualizes for the first time the 0.018" bracket slot deformation in a two brackets-archwire segment similar to torqueing in anterior region during orthodontic fixed appliance

therapy. The slot deformation seen is of clinical significance to orthodontists this might be a contributing factor for the torque loss.

Acknowledgement

Authors thank CAD lab and Metrology lab in the Department of Mechanical Engineering, SRM Institute of Science Technology, Kattankulathur, Chengalpattu, Tamil Nadu, India for provided facilities.

References

1. Andrea W, Guggenbühl S, Hötzel L, et al., Comparing Torque Transmission of Different Bracket Systems in Combination with Various Archwires Considering Play in the Bracket Slot: An In Vitro Study, *Materials*. 17(3): 684, 1-16 (2024).
2. Papageorgiou SN, Sifakakis I, Keilig L, et al., Torque differences according to tooth morphology and bracket placement: a finite element study, *Eur. J. Orthod.* 39(4), 411–418 (2017).
3. Bernisha RP, Mishra G, Pradeep Raj G, et al., Incisor torque expression characteristics in two passive self-ligating brackets placed at different heights. A finite element investigation, *J. Oral Biol. Craniofac. Res.* 14(1), 98-106 (2024).
4. Benaissa A, Merdji A, Bendjaballah MZ, et al., Stress influence on orthodontic system components under simulated treatment loadings, *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.* 195, 105569 (2020).
5. Chun, Y, Lee Y, Lee H, et al., Analytical study for prediction of stress distribution on orthodontic archwire considering short-term stress loss, *Comput. Methods Biomech. Biomed. Engin.* 26(14)1752–1760 (2022).
6. Lacoursiere RA, Nobes DS, Homeniuk DL, et al., Measurement of orthodontic bracket tie wing elastic and plastic deformation by arch wire torque expression utilizing an optical image correlation technique, *J Dent Biomech.* 1-8 397037 (2010).
7. Melenka GW, Nobes DS, Major PW, et al., Three-dimensional deformation of orthodontic brackets, *J of Dent Biomech.* 4, (2013).
8. Matsui S, Umezaki E, Komazawa D, et al., Evaluation of mechanical properties of esthetic brackets, *J Dent Biomech.* 26;6 (2015).
9. Magesh V, Harikrishnan P, Kingsly Jeba Singh D. Finite element analysis of slot wall deformation on stainless steel and titanium orthodontic brackets during simulated palatal root torque, *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 153(4), 481-488 (2018).
10. Harikrishnan P, Magesh V, Ajayan AM, et al., Finite element analysis of torque induced orthodontic bracket slot deformation in various bracket-archwire contact assembly, *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.* 197, 105748 (2020).
11. Magesh V, Harikrishnan P, Kingsly Jeba Singh D. Experimental evaluation of orthodontic bracket slot deformation to simulated torque, *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. H.* 235(8), 940-946 (2021).
12. Harikrishnan P, Magesh V. Comparative analysis of bracket deformation in tie wings and slot region during simulated torque by finite element analysis, *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 160(4), 588-593 (2021).
13. Harikrishnan P, Magesh V. Finite element analysis of Tie wings rotation – A new phenomenon in orthodontic bracket-archwire contact assembly during simulated torque, *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. H.* 236(11), 1626-1634 (2022).
14. Elsaka SE, Hammad SM, Ibrahim NF. Evaluation of stresses developed in different bracket-cement-enamel systems using finite element analysis with in vitro bond strength tests, *Prog Orthod.* 15,1-8 (2014).
15. Elias CN, Lima JHC, Valiev R, Meyers MA. Biomedical applications of titanium and its alloys. *Biol Mater Sci.* 60:46-49 (2008)
16. Dieter GE. In: *Mechanical metallurgy*. SI Metric ed. London, United Kingdom: Tata McGraw-Hill; 2013.